

Research Article

Concentration Reduction of Heavy Metals in Wastewater Using Potential Filamentous Fungi

Ahuchaogu, I. I., Etim, I, Nwaukwa, C. T. and Akpabio, A. J.
Department of Agricultural and Food Engineering, University of Uyo, Nigeria
*Corresponding author: israelahuchaogu@uniuyo.edu.ng

Abstract

The essence of this research was to determine the concentration of heavy metals in wastewater and to reduce their concentration to permissible limits set by World Health Organisation (WHO), Nigerian Standard for Drinking Water Quality (NSDWQ), and Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) standards. These three standards have been successfully used to measure the effectiveness of Potential Filamentous Fungi (PFF) in reducing the concentration of Heavy Metals (HM) from wastewater. There is dearth information in the use of PFF in attempting to reduce or eliminate HM concentration in wastewater in the study area hence the need for this research. Wastewater was sampled from three different locations (Abuloma jetty, Ozuboko waterside, and Amadi-Ama stream), and analysed to check the initial heavy metal concentration of wastewater. Isolated PFF was introduced to the sampled wastewater to reduce the concentration of HM, while Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS) was used for the sample analysis. The result shows that the concentration of some HM before the biosorption process was higher than the concentration after the biosorption process. PFF method was found suitable for the treatment of wastewater in relation to WHO, NSDWQ, and FAO standards. PFF method was found to be able to reduce the concentration of Arsenic (As), Nickel (Ni), Copper (Cu), Zinc (Zn), Lead (Pb), Chromium (Cr), and Vanadium (V) by 0%, 50.2%, 56%, 46.5%, 47.2%, 50%, and 0% respectively. PFF is a good absorbent of heavy metals since it has been able to reduce the concentration of heavy metals (such as Ni, Cu, Zn, Pb, Cr) except for As and V, and can be used to treat wastewater to achieve the permissible limits set by WHO, NSDWQ, and FAO standards.

Keywords: Filamentous fungi, Heavy metals, Treatment, Wastewater, Concentration, Biosorption.

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Introduction

Heavy metals according to Asha and Sandeep (2013), are generally defined as metals with relatively high densities, atomic weights or atomic numbers. More specific definitions have been published, but none of these have been widely accepted. Despite this lack of agreement, the term “heavy metals” is widely used in science. A density of more than 5 g/cm³ is sometimes quoted as a commonly used criterion for classifying metals as heavy (Asha and Sandeep, 2013). The earliest known metals such as Iron, Copper, and Tin, and precious metals such as Silver, Gold, and Platinum are heavy metals. Afterward, light metals, such as Magnesium, Aluminium, and Titanium, were discovered, as well as less well-known heavy metals including Gallium, Thallium, and Hafnium (Asha and Sandeep, 2013).

Industrialisation and extraction of natural resources have resulted in maximal environmental contaminations and pollutions. Contamination of soils, groundwater, sediments, surface water, and air with dangerous heavy metals and toxic chemicals is one of the major problems facing today’s world (Asha and Sandeep, 2013). The need to remediate the natural resources (soil, water, and air) has led to the development of advanced technologies that lay emphasis on the destruction of pollutants rather than the conventional approach of disposal because of their potential to enter the food chain (Asha and Sandeep, 2013). Contaminants (heavy metals) when present in plants and animals are capable of causing serious health problems, by interfering with normal life activities. Heavy metals and its toxicity could be transferred from contaminated irrigation water to plant, and the toxicity can be transferred from the plant to the seeds, fruits, and tuber, which may affect the consumer (Lacina *et al.*, 2013). Some of these metals are useful to the body in low concentration while some are harmful at high concentrations (Suranjana and Manas, 2009). Anthropogenic activities like metalliferous mining and smelting, agriculture, waste disposal or industrial discharge expose most of these variety of metals such as Silver (Ag), Arsenic (As), Gold (Au), Cadmium (Cd), Cobalt (Co), Chromium (Cr), Copper (Cu), Mercury (Hg), Nickel (Ni), Lead (Pb), Uranium (U), Zinc (Zn) into the environment (air, land and water) which can produce harmful effects on human health when they are taken in large amount that cannot be processed by humans and/or plants (Akshata *et al.*, 2012).

To successfully eliminate to acceptable (permissible) minimum level, fungi play a vital role in the bioremediation of contaminated soil and wastewater. In heavy metal contaminated environments, microbial populations adapt to a high concentration of

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heavy metals and become resistant to toxic concentration (Prasenjit and Sumathi, 2005). Some species of *Aspergillus* have been recorded as efficient Nickel and Chromium reducers (Yan and Viraraghavan, 2003). Recently, several filamentous fungi (FF) species were found to be useful for biological treatment of the sludge (settling, dewatering, organic compound degradation) under controlled operating conditions (Lacina, *et al.*, 2013). Therefore, it is a known fact that fungi have been founded to successfully and conveniently remove heavy metals contaminants from solution.

Thus, filamentous fungi have been used to reduce the concentration of heavy metals but no information exists to show that FF has been used to treat wastewater to recommended level of WHO (2011), NSDWQ (2007), and FAO (1990) standards. This is what this research intends to achieve by using isolated PFF or FF to reduce heavy metal concentration in wastewater. Heavy metal resistant fungi will be isolated and use for reduction of heavy metals in wastewater from Abuloma Jetty stream (AW), Amadi-Ama stream (AAW), and Ozuboko waterside (OW). The optimum pH and temperature levels of heavy metal removal will be determined for highly isolates of *Aspergillus* species along with the initial metal concentration and contact time.

Some heavy metals like nickel are needed by human in low concentration. Humans use Nickel as an ingredient of steel and other metals products. Foodstuffs have low concentration of natural Nickel but high amount can occur in food crops growing with polluted water (Oliver, 1997). Waste water from these study areas are contaminated by sewage and industrial effluents from the nearby industries and contains heavy metals and toxic chemicals, which is not safe for domestic, agricultural and industrial uses (Amadi, 2012). Plants growing in soils irrigated with heavy metal polluted water result to reduction in growth, performance, yield (Chibuike and Obiora, 2014) and causes cancer, organ damage, nervous system damage, and in extreme cases, death to human and livestock (Barakat, 2010). This research will promote the treatment of wastewater to enhance plant and animal growth. It will also give room to research on other sources of pollution and their effect in the study area as well as finding possible solutions to them.

Heavy metal removal from inorganic effluent can be achieved by conventional treatment processes such as chemical precipitation, ion exchange, and electrochemical removal. These processes have significant disadvantages, which are, for instance, incomplete removal, high-energy requirements, and production of toxic sludge (Babel and Kurniawan, 2004). Recently, numerous approaches have been adopted for the development of cheaper and more effective technologies, both to decrease the amount of

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wastewater produced and to improve the quality of the treated effluent. To this, adsorption has become one of the alternative treatments approaches. In recent years, the search for low-cost adsorbents that have metal-binding capacities has intensified. The adsorbents may be of mineral, organic or biological origin, Zeolites, industrial by-products, agricultural wastes, biomass, and polymeric materials (Kurniawan *et al.*, 2015). Membrane separation has been increasingly used recently for the treatment of inorganic effluent due to its convenient operation. There are different types of membrane filtration such as ultrafiltration (UF), nanofiltration (NF) and reverse osmosis (RO) (Kurniawan *et al.*, 2015). Electro-treatments such as electro-dialysis, has also contributed to environmental protection. Photocatalytic process is an innovative and promising technique for efficient destruction of pollutants in water (Skubal *et al.*, 2002). Although many techniques can be employed for the treatment of inorganic effluent, the ideal treatment should not be only suitable, appropriate and applicable to the local conditions, but also able to meet the maximum contaminant level (MCL) standards established. To highlight their removal performance, the main operating conditions such as pH and treatment efficiency are presented as well, (Pedersen, 2003).

Basically, two categorised methods are commonly used for bioremediation processes namely in-situ and ex-situ methods (Kumar *et al.*, 2011; Rayu *et al.*, 2012; Paliwal *et al.*, 2012). Ex-situ bioremediation methods commonly used and cited in literatures are: bioventing (USEPA, 2004; Robinson *et al.*, 2011); biosparging (USEPA, 2004; Machackova *et al.*, 2012); bioaugmentation (Cheng *et al.*, 2001; USEPA, 2004); biostimulation (Ma *et al.*, 2007; Baldwin *et al.*, 2008 and Fulekar *et al.*, 2012); biomineralization (Kim *et al.*, 2010); biosorption (Ahluwalia and Goyal, 2007; Abdel-Ghani *et al.*, 2007; Fiset *et al.*, 2008 and Machado *et al.*, 2010) and Phytoremediation (Pilon-Smits, 2005 and Kumar *et al.*, 2008). This study employed the ex-situ bioremediation approach in an attempt to reduce the concentration of heavy metal from wastewater.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

Wastewater was sampled from three different locations; Abuloma jetty, Ozuboko-Ama waterside, and Amadi-Ama stream. These locations are situated within Port-Harcourt city Local Government Area in Rivers State of Nigeria. Abuloma jetty is situated between latitude 4°46'16.07"N of the equator and longitude 7°3'36.74"E of the Greenwich meridian. Ozuboko-Ama is situated between latitude 4°46'28.31"N of the equator and longitude

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Figure 1: Map of Rivers State showing Port-Harcourt City Local Government Area (study area local government area). **Source:** Department of Geography Laboratory University of Uyo, 2017. Uyo, Akwa Ibom State

7°2'41.06^{II}E of the Greenwich meridian. Amadi-Ama stream is situated between latitude 4°47'48.29^{II}N of the equator and longitude 7°1'43.51^{II}E of the Greenwich meridian.

The study areas fall within the humid tropical forest climate (Amadi, 2012). The average rainfall for the area is about 2285mm and falls from March to November (Amadi, 2012). The study areas are approximately 5km apart from each other, and the temperature is

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Figure 2: Map of Port-Harcourt City Local Government showing sampling points (Abuloma stream, Ozuboko-Ama waterside, and Amadi-Ama stream). **Source:** Department of Geography Laboratory University of Uyo, 2017. Uyo, Akwa Ibom State

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highest in December and lowest in February due to harmatan (Amadi, 2012). The area is surrounded by mining and other industries and occupation of the natives are fishing and farming. Cassava, Maize, Yam, Banana are grown abundantly in the area (Amadi, 2012).

Sampling and sampling site

The main purpose of this research was to evaluate the tolerance potential of different isolated fungal strain towards heavy metals. For this purpose, wastewater was collected from three different locations; Abuloma jetty, Amadi-Ama Stream, and Ozuboko waterside. Wastewater from these three locations is known to be contaminated by sewage and industrial effluents from the nearby industries and contains heavy metals and toxic chemicals. These samples were stored in a freezer at a temperature of about -4°C so as to maintain its normal state (American Society of Testing and Material- ASTM D4691). The need for analysing samples at this stage was to determine the initial concentration of contaminants (heavy metals) in wastewater, so as to aid in comparing the differences between the initial sample state (before treatment) and the final state (after treatment). Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer was used for the analysis. The analysis was carried out in Technology Partners International Laboratories, No.137/139 Abuloma Road, Port-Harcourt, Rivers State.

Figure 3: Wastewater sampling process

Aspergillus fumigates are found in soils with decomposed materials but cannot be used for the biosorption process unless it is isolated and cultured (Shaja *et al.*, 2013). Measuring cylinder, weighing balance, pipette, petri dish, and incubator were the apparatus used to

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Figure 4: Samples of *Aspergillus fumigatus* (filamentous fungi) and autoclaves

achieve the isolation and culturing of the fungi. Following ASTM D4691 method, 1g of soil was weighed into 9ml of distilled water and homogenized to form a solution. 0.1mL of the solution was inaugurated into a petri-dish. Sabouraud dextrose Agar media was poured into the petri-dish containing 0.1ml of the solution to aid in fastening the growth of the fungi and to solidify the solution. The petri-dish was then inverted and incubated at 37°C for 3 to 5days so that colonies of fungi will be formed in the petri- dish (Iram *et al.*, 2013). The quantity of Filamentous fungi in each colony was about 1.0×10^6 CFU/ml. The fungal cultures were identified on the basis of macroscopic (colonial morphology, color, texture, shape, diameter and appearance of colony) and microscopic (septation in mycelium, presence of specific reproductive structures, shape and structure of conidia, and presence of sterile mycelium) characteristics (Zafar *et al.*, 2006). Pure cultures of fungi isolates were identified according to Domsch *et al.*, (1980) approach. Incubator, laminar flow equipment, autoclave, flame burner, rotary shaker, measuring cylinder, pipette, conical flask, and wire loop were major apparatus used in the preparation of heavy metal absorbent following methods described in ex-situ remediation processes (Ahluwalia and Goyal, 2007; Abdel-Ghani *et al.*, 2007; Fiset *et al.*, 2008 and Machado *et al.*, 2010). Materials (items) such as distilled water, cotton plug, potato dextrose (PD) broth media, industrial glucose, aluminium foil were used to actualised the preparation. Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) such as hand gloves, nose mask, lab coat, safety shoes etc were worn for safety purposes. Following Iram, *et al.*, (2013) approach, *Aspergillus fumigatus* biomass was prepared (Figure 4) in PD broth (potato dextrose broth) media. To prepare 100 ml of

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the PD broth, 30ml of potato broth and 2 gm of glucose were added in conical flask and fill it up to 100ml of distilled water. Flask was tightly closed with a cotton plug and then aluminium foil and autoclaved at 121°C and 15 Pascal for 20 minutes. Later on, the flask was opened under laminar flow and three colonies of fungus are inoculated into each flask. The flask was agitated on a rotary shaker for 3-4 days at 150 rpm and at 30°C temperature. After 3-4 days thick bed of fungal biomass developed was used for biosorption experiments using AAS. To investigate the biosorption capacity of the several *Aspergillus fumigatus* isolates towards the heavy metals with various initial heavy metal concentrations and optimal cultural conditions, metal solution standards of 200ppm, 100ppm, 10ppm, 5.0ppm, 1.5ppm, 1.0ppm, and 0.5ppm were diluted from 1000ppm stock standard of Cu, Pb, Zn, Cr, Ni, V, and Cd for metals Copper, Lead, Zinc, Chromium, Nickel Vanadium and Cadmium respectively to check the equipment (Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS)) calibration (Vanloon and Lichwa, 1973).

$$C_1V_1 = C_2 V_2 \qquad 1$$

Where C_1 = concentration of the stock standard, ppm, C_2 = concentration of the standard to be diluted, ppm; V_1 = volume of stock standard used, ml; V_2 = volume of distilled water (ml) was used according to Darell and Steven (2005). Subsequent to metal solution preparation, 1 gm of fungal biomass was suspended in 100 ml of wastewater in 250ml conical flask. The flasks were agitated on a rotary shaker at 150rpm and at 30°C with contact time of 4 hrs. Thereafter, the water samples were filtered before being run with AAS (Vanloon and Lichwa, 1973).

For the determination of heavy metals, the Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS) was powered on and warmed up for 30 min. After the heating of cathode lamp, air acetylene flame was ignited and the instrument was calibrated or standardized with different working standards (Vanloon and Lichwa, 1973). Thereafter the water samples were ran with AAS and concentrations of different metals were processed and recorded in a computer system aided by AAS-Wizard software.

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Results and Discussion

Table 1: Presentation of heavy metals concentrations of wastewater from Abuloma stream, Ozuboko waterside, and Amadi-Ama stream, with their statistical values.

S/N	Heavy metals	AW ₁ (ppm)	OW ₁ (ppm)	AAW ₁ (ppm)	Mean	± SD	VAR
1	Arsenic (As)	-0.352	-0.523	-0.536	-0.472	±0.10	0.012
2	Nickel (Ni)	0.092	0.023	0.017	0.044	±0.04	0.002
3	Copper (Cu)	0.367	0.267	0.253	0.296	±0.06	0.004
4	Zinc (Zn)	0.140	0.120	0.122	0.127	±0.01	0.000
5	Lead (Pb)	0.154	0.076	0.072	0.101	±0.05	0.002
6	Chromium (Cr)	0.144	0.075	0.080	0.100	±0.04	0.002
7	Vanadium (V)	-0.109	-0.191	-0.150	-0.150	±0.04	0.002

AW₁ = Concentration Wastewater from Abuloma stream before treatment; OW₁ = Concentration Wastewater from Ozuboko-Ama waterside before treatment; AAW₁ = Concentration Wastewater from Amadi-Amadi stream before treatment; SD = Standard deviation of the three locations; VAR = Variance of the three locations, all values are approximated to three decimal place.

The mean concentration of Arsenic obtained was -0.47193 ppm (Table 1) and the deviation from the mean was 0.10. Comparing the mean concentration of Arsenic in wastewater from these three locations (Abuloma jetty, Ozuboko-Ama, and Amadi-Ama waterside) with WHO (2011), NSDWQ (2007) and FAO (1990) standards, wastewater from these locations was discovered to be safe since their mean (-0.47193ppm) was lower than the maximum permissible limits of standards used which were 0.01ppm, 0.01ppm, and 0.1ppm respectively. The concentration of Nickel was 0.04422ppm and the deviation from the mean was 0.04. Comparing these values with standards adopted, wastewater from these locations was noticed to be safe since their mean values were less than the maximum permissible limit (0.07ppm and 0.2ppm respectively) except for NSDWQ. The mean concentration of Copper was 0.2957ppm and the deviation from the mean was 0.06 which was found to be safe in terms of comparing with the adopted standards. The mean concentration of Zinc was 0.127400ppm, and the deviation from the mean was 0.01. The mean concentration of Lead was 0.100700ppm, and the deviation from the mean was 0.05, which was found to be greater the permissible limits by WHO and NSDWQ but not for

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FAO. Comparing the mean value of zinc with WHO (2011), NSDWQ (2007), and FAO (1990) standards, wastewater from these three locations were found safe. The mean concentration of Chromium was 0.099900ppm, and the deviation from the mean was 0.04 which was found to be safe. The mean concentration of Vanadium was -0.15040ppm, and the deviation from the mean was 0.04 was found safe comparing the mean value of Vanadium with WHO (2011), NSDWQ (2007), and FAO (1990) standards.

Table 2: Presentation of Heavy metals standards

S/N	Heavy Metals	WHO, 2011 (ppm)	NSDWQ, 2007 (ppm)	FAO,1990 (ppm)
1	Arsenic (As)	0.01	0.01	0.10
2	Nickel (Ni)	0.07	0.02	0.20
3	Copper (Cu)	2.00	1.00	0.20
4	Zinc (Zn)	3.00	3.00	2.00
5	Lead (Pb)	0.01	0.01	5.00
6	Chromium (Cr)	0.05	0.05	0.10
7	Vanadium (V)	0.00	0.00	0.10

WHO = World Health Organization; NSDWQ = Nigerian Standard for Drinking Water Quality; FAO = Food and Agricultural Organization (Pratt and Suarez, 1990; Barakat, 2010; NCP, 2010)

Table 3: Presentation of Heavy metals concentration result of Wastewater from Abuloma stream

S/N	Heavy Metals	AW ₁ (ppm)	AW ₂ (ppm)	WHO,2008 (ppm)	NSDWQ,2007 (ppm)	FAO,1990 (ppm)
1	Arsenic (As)	-0.352	-0.352	0.010	0.010	0.100
2	Nickel (Ni)	0.092	0.058	0.070	0.020	0.200
3	Copper (Cu)	0.367	0.224	2.000	1.000	0.200
4	Zinc (Zn)	0.140	0.072	3.000	3.000	2.000
5	Lead (Pb)	0.154	0.086	0.010	0.010	5.000
6	Chromium (Cr)	0.144	0.079	0.050	0.050	0.100
7	Vanadium (V)	-0.109	-0.109	0.000	0.000	0.100

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Table 4: Presentation of Heavy metals concentration of Wastewater from Ozuboko-Ama waterside

S/N	Heavy Metals	OW ₁ (ppm)	OW ₂ (ppm)	WHO,2008 (ppm)	NSDWQ,2007 (ppm)	FAO,1990 (ppm)
1	Arsenic (As)	-0.528	-0.528	0.010	0.010	0.100
2	Nickel (Ni)	0.023	0.012	0.070	0.020	0.200
3	Copper (Cu)	0.267	0.172	2.000	1.000	0.200
4	Zinc (Zn)	0.120	0.052	3.000	3.000	2.000
5	Lead (Pb)	0.076	0.026	0.010	0.010	5.000
6	Chromium (Cr)	0.075	0.043	0.050	0.050	0.100
7	Vanadium (V)	-0.191	-0.191	0.000	0.000	0.100

Table 5: Result of heavy metals concentration of Wastewater from Amadi- Ama stream

S/N	Heavy Metals	AAW ₁ (ppm)	AAW ₂ (ppm)	WHO,2008 (ppm)	NSDWQ,2007 (ppm)	FAO,1990 (ppm)
1	Arsenic (As)	-0.536	-0.536	0.010	0.010	0.100
2	Nickel (Ni)	0.017	0.006	0.070	0.020	0.200
3	Copper (Cu)	0.253	0.120	2.000	1.000	0.200
4	Zinc (Zn)	0.122	0.054	3.000	3.000	2.000
5	Lead (Pb)	0.072	0.039	0.010	0.010	5.000
6	Chromium (Cr)	0.080	0.031	0.050	0.050	0.100
7	Vanadium (V)	-0.150	-0.150	0.000	0.000	0.100

From Tables 3, 4, and 5 filamentous fungi method was found not suitable for reducing the concentration of Arsenic in wastewater irrespective of location, based on the three standards employed. However, the concentration of Nickel was reduced from 0.0923ppm to 0.0577ppm in wastewater gotten from Abuloma stream, 0.0231ppm to 0.0115ppm in wastewater gotten from Ozuboko-Ama waterside, and 0.0173ppm to 0.0058ppm in wastewater gotten from Amadi-Ama stream. From statistics, the efficiency of filamentous fungi to reduce the concentration of Nickel in wastewater gotten from these three locations was higher in Abuloma (65%), Ozuboko-Ama (50%), and Amadi-Ama (35.5%) in wastewater respectively. Copper (Cu) was reduced from 0.3673ppm to 0.2242ppm,

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0.2672ppm to 0.1717ppm, and 0.02528ppm to 0.1092ppm in wastewater gotten from Abuloma stream, Ozuboko waterside, and Amadi-Ama stream respectively. From statistics, the efficiency of filamentous fungi to reduce copper concentration in wastewater decreased progressively from 64% (Ozuboko), 61% (Abuloma) to 43% (Amadi-Ama) from statistical analysis. The Filamentous fungi method was found to be effective in reducing the concentration of Zinc in wastewater with efficiencies of 51.6%, 43.4%, and 44.5% in wastewater from Abuloma stream, Ozuboko waterside, and Amadi-Ama stream respectively. Apart from Arsenic, Nickel, Copper, Zinc were found to fall within the limit for potable considering WHO, NSDWQ and FAO standards.

The concentration of Lead in these three locations was higher for in terms of potability considering WHO (2011) and NSDWQ (2007) limits hence water from the three sources are not safe for drinking. This is an indication that filamentous fungi method was ineffective. Filamentous fungi method proved a good method of reducing the concentration of Chromium (Cr) in wastewater. The result shows that concentration of Chromium could be reduced from 0.1441ppm to 0.0786ppm, 0.0753ppm to 0.0426ppm, and 0.0803ppm to 0.0311ppm in wastewater from Abuloma stream, Ozuboko waterside, and Amadi-Ama stream respectively. From statistics, the efficiency of fungi to reduce the concentration of Chromium in these locations are 54.5%, 56.6%, and 38.7% for wastewater gotten from Abuloma stream, Ozuboko waterside, and Amadi-Ama stream respectively. Though the reduction does not make the water safe for consumption since the trace of Chromium exceeded the limits from the considered standards.

The Filamentous fungi method did not prove effective in reduction of Vanadium concentration in wastewater neither could the results obtained showed it effective in reducing Vanadium to acceptable limit for drinking, (WHO, 2011; NSDWQ, 2007 and FAO, 1990).

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Table 6: Summary of Statistical values from the three locations

Group	Count	Sum*	Average*	Variance*	Source of Variation	SS*	Df*	MS*	F*	P-value*	F-Crit*
AW1	7	0.437	0.062	0.052682	Between Groups	0.010	1	0.010	0.236	0.636	4.747
AW2	7	0.057	0.008	0.034603	Within Groups	0.524	12	0.044			
					Total	0.534	13				
OW1	7	-0.157	-0.023	0.068204	Between Groups	0.005	1	0.005	0.077	0.786	4.747
OW2	7	-0.415	-0.059	0.054202	Within Groups	0.734	12	0.061			
					Total	0.739	13				
AAW1	7	0.340	0.049	0.016613	Between Groups	0.055	1	0.055	1.759	0.209	4.747
AAW2	7	-0.537	-0.077	0.045845	Within Groups	0.375	12	0.031			
					Total	0.430	13				

Abuloma (AW), Ozuboko (OW) and Amadi-Ama (AAW) using ANOVA (Single factor) at significant level of 0.05 ($P < 0.05$). 1= before treatment; 2= after treatment; SS = Sum of squares; Df = degree of freedom; MS = Mean square; F = F-ratio; P-value = probability value

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The Probability-values (0.636, 0.786 and 0.209) for Abuloma (AW), Ozuboko-Ama (OW) and Amadi-Ama (AAW) respectively from Table 6 show that there was no reduction in the concentration of heavy metals (Adam and Mark, 2013). Although there was a significant percentage reduction in some heavy metals concentration after treatment with potential filamentous fungi (AW: Ni=65%, Cu=61%, Zn=51%, Pb=55.6%, Cr=54.5%), (OW: Ni=50%, Cu=64%, Zn=43%, Pb=31%, Cr=56%) and (AAW: Ni=35%, Cu=43%, Zn=44.5%, Pb=54.6%, Cr=38.7%) which cannot be shown statistically due to close range value between wastewater concentration before and after treatments, (Adam and Mark, 2013).

Conclusion

The essence of this research was to determine the concentration of heavy metals in wastewater and the effectiveness of PFF (*Aspergillus fumigatus*) to reduce the concentration of detected HM to permissible limits based on (WHO.2011; NSDWQ, 2007 and FAO, 1990) standards. From the research results, potential filamentous fungi (PFF) played a crucial and significant role in reducing the concentration of some heavy metals in wastewater, although they cannot be completely eliminated. With the wide percentage reduction of heavy metals in wastewater from the results, it was shown statistically that there was no reduction, due to the close range value between the wastewater concentration before and after treatment.

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